

STRUCTURAL SEMANTIC TYPES OF NON-EXPANDED SENTENCES

Semantics and Syntax

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Abstract

The urgency and novelty of the given investigated work consists that work is devoted studying and consideration on a concrete material of not widespread two-member verbal offers, to studying of a question on properties of the syntactic semantics which is one of questions at issue of a modern science about language. In first half 80th years it is marked by the further increase of interests of linguists to the semantic party of the statement, transition from the declaration of a role of semantics in syntactic designing to realization of this idea in practice of concrete researches.

Attentions of scientists involve not the facts existing in language, but deep processes connected with lexical role, syntactic, denotation, etc. Such turn of interests of scientists to language allowed them, as though highlighting studied object from within, going from means to forms, finding out in the organization of syntactic sentence structure its parts which remained invisible earlier. It can be tracked on an example of unexpanded two-structured verbal sentences.

In traditional grammar typological differences of sentences to signs of expanded / unexpanded sentences, completeness/incompleteness, on structure are shown, complexities etc. We have now detailed data about sentence parts, functions and morphological forms of their expression etc.

However the description based mainly on formal signs of presence and absence of the main members or minor members at them, does not give us full picture of formation and functioning of sentences in speech, remain many questions connected with the organization of their internal semantic structure.

So, for example, we know, that sentences in which there are no minor members are called as unexpanded, but we do not know, why one main member have minor members, and others don't have and also what semantic classes of lexical units are capable to take positions of the main sentence parts. There are two examples: *Pupil reads* and also *pupil reads a book*. Whether there is dependence between formations of two different types of sentences and those lexical units («pupil», «to read» and «magazine») which fill their block diagrammes?

To answer this question it is possible, only having addressed to syntactic properties of the lexical values which are the basic building material for formed sentences, means to the organization of their semantic structure.

Acquaintance with the literature devoted to studying of syntactic properties of lexemes and their means, allowed to systematize diverse forms and directions of using of verbs and dependent from them nouns in 16 types, to explain the organization of semantic structure of word-combinations and offers, in particular organization of semantic structure of unexpanded two-structured verbal sentences syntactic properties of lexemes entering into them.

The lexical word meanings analyzed in the given work, appeared heterogeneous on syntactic properties of their compatibility.

1. It is combined necessarily with the lexemes acting as the main sentence parts, for example,

Father is having a rest.

Summer has come.

Factory works...

2. It is obligatory with lexemes as minor members, for example,

Collective farmers are picking up cotton.

The father looks through the newspaper.

3. It is obligatory with lexemes in the form of an oblique case, for example,

Child is ill.

He is not sleeping.

4. It is combined with lexemes as facultative minor members, for example,

Father is having a rest at home.

Factory works smoothly.

Summer has quickly come.

Later L.V. Sherba, taking into account signs of syntactic compatibility of lexemes of G.A. Zolotova, distinguishes absolute and relative lexical word meanings. G.A. Zolotova defines: "Words with absolute meaning – *a table, a house, pleasure to breathe, sit, quickly, kind* and etc. – possess sufficient semantic completeness in order not to require in obligatory completion. They can be extended by others; by one words: *a desk, a table from plastic, a table for work, a strong wind, a wind from the south to breathe deeply, to breathe a nose*, and etc., but they do not demand this distribution" (Zolotova, 1973). Now the attention of researchers involves more and more the role of lexical word meanings in their syntactic designing. L.N. Murzin writes: «If the predicate designates the action closed in object (compare absolute means) forms two structured nuclear sentence (*child sleeps, the Sun shines, car works.*)» (Murzin, 1974).

Possibility of formation certain syntactic structures are concluded in the lexical and grammatical nature of words, appearing in syntactic relations in the sentence. Relative meanings designate not only separate subjects and the reality phenomena, but also some kind of “events” with their participants.

So, for example, in relative meaning of a verb «to write» («*in writing to make any text*») we can find an instructions on the person who possesses this action, and on object on which this action is directed. Hence, it contains three participants of the «event»-«the person-subject», his “action” and object of this “action”. Realizing meaning «*in writing to make any text*», we receive the following structure, like «*brother is writing the letter*», «*He is writing report*», «*Sister is writing the statement*», etc.

The interesting idea on this question is stated by F. Danesh. Analyzing structure of verbal values and their role in sentence formation, he writes, what even the grammatical incorrectly constructed statement, like «*Any person to bring you the book*» («*Какой-то человек принести вы книгу*»), can be understood correctly by the listener because verb to «bring» is perceived by it as transitive, operating accusative and plus dative cases and as personal.

A combination «*Any person*» receives function of the manufacturer of action, the lexeme the «*book*» taking of a position of object, carries out passive function and, at last, a lexeme «*you*» - function of the dative addressee.

Using absolute or relative meanings should be understood not simply as their realization in speech, and as the realization leading to formation of communicative or not communicative syntactic units of certain structure.

Realizing absolute meanings, for example, «ability to action, ability or employment in general», verbs «to write, to read», etc. act as predicates of unexpanded two-structured verbal sentence «*brother writes*», «*brother reads*», and realizing relative sentence. For example, graphic signs to express the thoughts «to write» or visually to perceive written by graphic signs «to read», the same verbs promote formation widespread two-member verbal – «*brother is writing report*» «*brother is reading the letter*».

Thanks to allocation of verbs with absolute and relative values it became possible to interpret in a new fashion the phenomenon unexpanded/expanded sentences, to see and describe laws of formation of semantic structures of expanded two-structured verbal sentences.

At the present stage of development of syntactic science studying of language units of any level without the reference to their substantial party is already impossible. «What we ever did, - wrote E. Benveniste, - not to take into consideration meaning, to avoid it and to get off it., but it, as a head of the Jellyfish, always in the language centre, bewitching those who beholds it».

The impossibility of ignoring of the substantial party of language speaks that last, on the one hand, is in close dialectic unity with formal-grammatical part of its expression and, on the other hand, its formal-grammatical and substantial parts forming unity of the form and the maintenance, originally influence against each other.

Categorical, typical syntactic and concrete lexical meanings are in turn allocated from objectively existing language units: the first - from means of lexical and grammatical categories of words as the parts of speech, the second - from means of the lexical units which are carrying out or capable to execute the same syntactic function, and the third - from this positions, that in speech the word realizes only one of the values. And lexical values realized in the offer suppose ordering not on their accessory to this or that part of speech, a stylistic layer and not alphabetically, and on the basis of their functional generality and syntactic compatibility.

The basic theoretical positions of article are formulated on the basis of studying of works of scientists V. G. Gak, G. A. Zolotov, N. Yu. Shvedova, Yu. D. Arutunova etc., devoted to a question of the semantic nature of offers. The actual material is used in work for the analysis of semantic structures of unexpanded two-structured verbal sentences, taken from Russian literatures, and from journalese editions and informal conversation.

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